

REQUIREMENTS OF THE PERIOD OF THE POLICY OF CONSTITUTIONAL SECURITY OF RIGHTS, FREEDOMS AND LEGAL ADVANTAGES OF WOMEN IN UZBEKISTAN

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Key concepts: person who committed domestic violence, socio-demographic characteristics, personality of the offender, level of criminality of the person.

Abstract: The article presents the reforms and their content, as well as opinions and comments on early prevention of harassment and violence against women.

In our country, special attention is paid to strengthening the legal framework for early crime prevention based on an in-depth study and scientific analysis of the conditions that allow for the commission of harassment and violence against women. In particular, a comprehensive study of offenses, crime, family conflicts and violence, family divorces and their social consequences,[1] identifying and analyzing the causes of domestic violence, factors that trigger suicidal moods,[2] as well as teaching the legal and psychological foundations of resolving family conflict situations, preventing divorces[3] is being adopted, and effective preventive measures are being taken to prevent offenses in this regard.

It should be noted that our current legislation contains norms prohibiting harassment and violence against women, not subjecting a person to violence, torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment and punishment. In particular, Article 25 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "The right to life is an inalienable right of every person and is protected by law." Assassination of human life is the most serious crime," Article 26 states that "No one shall be subjected to torture, violence, other cruel inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment," Article 27 states that "Everyone has the right to freedom and personal inviolability." [4] In particular, the presence of such norms as "Women and men have equal rights" in Article 58 serves to protect the rights and freedoms of women.

It should be noted that in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2020, No. UP-5938 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the mahalla institution, and bring the system of work with families and women to a new level," a new system based on the principle of "prosperous and safe mahalla" was introduced, providing for the following areas:

transforming the makhalla institution, which is a unique social structure of society, into a true confidant and supporter of the population, increasing its role and significance;

supporting the social activity of women, strengthening their place in society, strengthening guarantees for the protection of their rights and legitimate interests;

radical reform of organizational and legal mechanisms for ensuring a healthy and stable socio-spiritual environment and peace, harmony and tranquility in society and the family;

establishment of continuous, systematic interaction of the mahalla institute with internal affairs bodies, other state bodies and public organizations;

further increasing the role and status of employees of self-government bodies of citizens and prevention inspectors;

introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the sphere and decent stimulation of the work of employees and improvement of material and technical support.

The introduction of this system serves to further strengthen the role and position of the mahalla in ensuring the well-being of the population, raising the quality of work with families and women to a new level, increasing the social activity of the elderly, and turning the mahalla into a crime-free zone.

Today, at the initiative of the head of our state, mechanisms have been created to listen to the concerns of women and solve their daily problems in the mahalla. A system has been created to provide close assistance to women in any difficult situation, such as family conflicts, mental or physical violence, violations of the right to work or study.

In this regard, in the system of internal affairs bodies alone, about 340 female inspectors provide psychological, legal and social assistance to women suffering from such problems.

Another important aspect of the new system is that women no longer need to go to any government agency to solve their family problems. Now there are opportunities to identify and solve their problems through door-to-door visits.

In particular, call centers "1259" and "1286" with short numbers have been established for the early detection of cases of violence against women, and about 9,000 women have been provided with legal and psychological assistance.

Also, based on the experience of Turkey, an electronic program "E-Himoya" was created for mobile phones to prevent women from becoming victims of domestic violence and crime.

With this program, the "SOS" button is installed on the phone, and when pressing it, the location of the person is visible in the duty units of the internal affairs bodies, and a prevention inspector is sent to the scene of the incident. This program will be gradually implemented in all regions of the republic.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Further Improvement of the System of Reliable Protection of the Rights, Freedoms and Legitimate Interests of Women and Children" adopted on April 11, 2023, introduced new mechanisms aimed at fully ensuring the rights of women in our country. In particular, for the first time, "family violence" was assessed as a separate act, and norms of administrative and criminal liability for persons who committed it were established.

Also, to the Law "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence":

- a new concept called "harassment" was introduced;
- a norm has been established that prohibits the simultaneous presence of a person who has committed violence at work and a person who has suffered from it;
- the validity period of the "protection order" has been extended from 1 month to 1 year.

These mechanisms will serve to more effectively organize our work to prevent any crimes or offenses that may be committed against our women. After all, in the words of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, no woman should have tears!"

Protective orders were issued to 39,263 women who were harassed or abused in 2023. At the same time, administrative measures were taken against 3,111 persons (Article 2061 of the Code of Administrative Offenses) who did not comply with the requirements of the

protection order and were prone to committing harassment and violence without complying with the established restrictions. Also, as a result of conducting individual preventive work with about 26,000 women who committed crimes or offenses in their places of residence, the total number of crimes committed by women by the end of 12 months of 2023 decreased to 488 (13,465/12,977) or 3.6%, as well as murder (37/25), grievous bodily harm (114/75), fraud (3167/2828).

It should be noted that as a result of the implementation of the new system, for 12 months of 2023:

- 6,634 women were employed jointly;
- 8,473 people received material and social assistance;
- 1,683 people received medical care;
- 1,705 people's identity documents were restored;
- 1,996 people were closely assisted in their entrepreneurial activities.

Also, 632 girls who did not attend school were identified and returned to educational institutions to continue their education, while 1,450 women who were in a difficult social situation and were prone to suicide were placed in "Women's Rehabilitation and Adaptation Centers." [6]

The problems of 44,281 families with conflict situations within the family life were considered in the mahalla itself, and as a result of eliminating the unrest of 25,751, 11,603 families were saved from separation.

As a result of joint preventive measures, 26,100 women, including 647 minors and 5,076 young girls (18-30 years old), were removed from the preventive account of the internal affairs bodies due to the transition to a healthy lifestyle from 35,175 women on preventive account.

Restrictions were imposed on 37,524 individuals who had been subjected to violence or harassment, 20,753 families were reconciled and the root causes of 17,884 disputes were resolved as a result of addressing the problems of individuals who had been issued a "protection order." [7]

To date, 290,475 individuals have been identified and their lists have been compiled in civil and administrative courts regarding issues related to family and marital relations.

Among them:

- 137,695 divorces;
- 85,356 alimony;
- 5,714 people were forcibly placed in housing;
- 349 - restoration of parental rights and return of the child;
- 851 people objected to paternity status;
- 2.145 people were deprived of parental rights;
- Cancellation of 193 adoptions;
- 53,397 constitute other cases related to family and marital relationships. [8]

In October 2023, more than 215,000 families of this category were studied with mahalla activists and measures were taken to solve their problems.

Also, in order to provide urgent necessary assistance to women in difficult situations, a "Trust Center" was created in the system (as part of the Crime Prevention Service, from January 10, 2022) with short numbers "1259" and "1286" and psychological and legal assistance was provided to 9,297 women who called this center over the past period.

To protect women from harassment and violence, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

First of all, he has been disputing with the courts for the last three years

It is necessary to take measures to resolve conflicts in more than 25,000 families in peaceful years. If their problems are not addressed in a timely manner, they can lead to the commission of serious and especially serious crimes.

Secondly, there is a need to create joint mobile groups to resolve conflicts. This will create an opportunity to accelerate work to identify the problems of women living in remote areas directly at home and solve them systematically.

Thirdly, in order to prevent women from becoming victims of offenses by providing them with jobs and creating a permanent source of income for them, it is necessary to work in cooperation with responsible organizations in the direction of training unemployed women in professions in demand in the labor market.

Fourthly, in order to find a place for women in society and protect their rights, it is necessary to systematically establish the practice of organizing mobile receptions in each district in cooperation with district officials at least once a week.

It is no secret that Uzbek women do not share their problems with many people due to their modesty and centuries-old traditions. Therefore, it is possible to systematically establish this work practice and provide them with close assistance and solve their problems on the spot.

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